

Modified Lower Bound Theorem for Comparison Based Sorting Algorithms

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Abstract — The work presented over here proposes a modified theorem for lower bound of sequential comparison based sorting algorithms where the decision of sorting has already been taken. There is much advancement in the field of computation especially in the field algorithms, use of multiple cores or processors, availability of cloud and lowering the cost of various hardware components etc. All these advancements has led to change in the users the requirements and the way the requirements can be fulfilled. Keeping all these advancements in mind here is an effort to redefine the classical theorem so that problem of sorting can be further understood and improved as current theorem addresses only time complexity.

Keywords—Sorting, Lower Bound Theorem, Comparison based Sorting, Time Complexity, Space Complexity, Processor Complexity, Structural Complexity, Bandwidth Complexity, Interface Complexity, Stable Algorithms.

I. INTRODUCTION

Sorting algorithms are one of the intensively used algorithms in the field of computing. It has cascading effect which keeps on multiplying itself as soon as we change the level of working. If we improve the time and space complexities involved in the sorting algorithms, it would improve the efficiency of all the related processes in a cascading manner like Operating System and then Networking algorithms then Image Processing then Machine Learning then Security Algorithms and so on. This paper addresses some key areas of improvements by modifying lower bound theorem of comparison based sorting algorithms. It further suggests the strategies and reasoning to improve and modify the Lower Bound Theorem for comparison based sequential sorting algorithms. Efforts are there to reduce the time complexities but at the cost of space complexity, processor complexity, bandwidth complexity to name a few.

II. COMPARISON BASED SORTING ALGORITHMS

Comparison based sorting algorithms are the algorithms which sorts a sequence using comparison as the basic most generic operation. There are immense number of algorithms based on comparison as unit operation for example Heap Sort and Merge Sort to name a few which are claimed to be efficient most algorithms as far as time complexities are concern. Lower Bound Theorem for comparison sort is extensively used to prove efficacy of various sorting algorithms [1]. Merge Sort claims $\Omega(n \log n)$ time complexity but at the cost of space complexity of $\Omega(n)$, reason being that merge sort requires additional memory of equal size[2]. Heap Sort also claims $\Omega(n \log n)$ time complexity but at the cost of space complexity of $\Omega(\log n)$, reason being that heap sort requires additional memory of $\log_2 n$ size[3]. Heap Sort does include internal processing complexity also which is hidden. On the other hand we have non-comparison based algorithms also for example Counting Sort which claims linear complexity of $O(n+k)$ but that is also at the cost of additional memory requirement of $O(k)$, here n is the size of sequence and k is the range of spread of these n values[1]. Besides that counting sort also put restriction to use sequence of integers only which is practical applicable to most of the problems. Provided linear complexities at the cost of space complexities we have variety of algorithms which offer $O(1)$ space complexity but considered inferior due to their time complexity. For example bubble sort the worst one from the point of view of time but best from the point of view of space. A comparative study of tradeoffs are shown below in table 1.

Algorithm	Worst Case Time Complexity	Worst Case Space Complexity	Stability	Structural Complexity	Processor Complexity	Tradeoff
Bubble Sort	$O(n^2)$	$O(1)$	Stable	Array	None	Already Poor time complexity
Insert Sort	$O(n^2)$	$O(n)$	Stable	Array	None	Already Poor time complexity
Selection Sort	$O(n^2)$	$O(1)$	Stable	Link List	None	Already Poor time complexity
Quick Sort	$O(n^2)$	$O(n)$	Unstable	Array	None	Already Poor time complexity
Heap Sort	$\Omega(n \log n)$	$O(1)$	Stable	Heap	None	Trade off is Structural

						Complexity
Merge Sort	$\Theta(n \log n)$	$O(n)$	Stable	Array	None	Trade off is Space Complexity
Parallel Merge Sort	$\Theta(\log n)^3$	$O(n)$	Stable	Array	$O(n/2)$	Trade off is Processor Complexity

Table 1: Tradeoff complexities factors for various well known sorting algorithms

III. PROCESSOR COMPLEXITY IN LIEU OF TIME COMPLEXITY

There are lot of developments on PRAM (Parallel Random Access Models) algorithms which are offering time complexities even lesser than linear time complexities but at the cost of processor complexity. It rather increase hardware cost but the reasonability of such type of algorithm is justified for mission critical processes only where cost is ignored with respect to outcome. Marszałek Z. has presented in his article Parallelized Modified Merge Sort based on PRAM(Parallel Random Access Machine) algorithm which can be used for sorting of large data sets rapidly. Parallelized Modified Merge Sort based on PRAM Model was proved to sort n elements in the maximum time $2n \cdot \log_2 n - 2$ using n processors but the problem remain same that here trade off is number of processors[5]. Few more new algorithms are suggested to lower the sorting time for example GPU-based sorting algorithm, which can achieve high performance to sort large-scale in-memory data using GPU processors. It consists of two algorithms: the first one is an in-core algorithm, which is responsible for sorting data in GPU global memory and second one is an out-of-core algorithm, which is responsible for dividing large-scale data into multiple chunks that fit GPU global memory[6][7] here again the catch is use of extra processor in form of GPU as well as extra space to manage structural and process related requirements. Almost all the sequential algorithms have their PRAM Counterparts with lesser time complexity but with increased cost of processors. We will call it processor complexity here onwards.

IV. SPACE COMPLEXITY IN LIEU OF TIME COMPLEXITY

The worst considered Bubble Sort or selection sort is considered worst due to their time complexities. But these may appear good as far as space complexities are concerned. Merge and Heap Sort provides linear complexities for time but not for space. Though there are many improvements suggested for example Triple Heap Sorting Algorithm which is again concentrating on time complexity and claim to achieve Lower bound in better manner than Binary Heap Sorting Algorithm but it is also at the cost of increased space complexity [8]. Idea of phase wise and segmentation[9] are presented by many researchers which establishes the need of including many other parameters in lower bound theorem to make the comparison based sorting model complete. So this is the time to adjust various tradeoffs between space and time complexities and we need to extend lower bound theorem inclusive of other tradeoff aspects. This tradeoff is depicted in Figure 1 where an even bubble sort appears better than Merge and Heap Sort as far as space complexity is concerned.

Figure 1: Space Complexity tradeoff: Inferior time Bubble Sort appears better than superior time Merge Sort as far as space is concerned for large data sets.

V. STRUCTURAL COMPLEXITY

Besides Processor and space complexities there are other trade off complexity factors also exists. Here these complexities involved to maintain underlying data structure. For example as shown in Figure 2 in Heap sort to maintain heap we must spare some complexity which is not necessarily comparison based but additional burden to maintain heap and then adjusting it again on deletion of minimum. As it is already established that when we remove minimum from a min heap it adjusts itself which can again take $O(\log n)$ time and this adjustment is repeated n times for every removal from heap. Effectively complexity of $O(n \log n)$ is repeated twice. Once when we form the heap and second when we extract the minimum. Rather it has been established the heaps are not better than merge sort as far as sorting is concerned but they are still good to implement priority queue [1].

Figure 2: Structural Complexity tradeoff: Heap sort not only suffers from space complexity for large data sets but suffers from structural complexity also.

VI. CLASSICAL LOWER BOUND THEOREM FOR COMPARISON BASED SORTING ALGORITHMS

It States that “Any Comparison Based sorting algorithm will take at least $\Omega(n \log n)$ comparison in worst case”. There are many corollaries also of lower bound theorem for comparison based sorting algorithms. As per this theorem Heap Sort and Merge Sort are the algorithms which have achieved the lower bound [10]. Though there are many other corollaries also which means the same thing that no algorithm is possible which can take less than $\Omega(n \log n)$ comparisons. Based on this theorem Merge Sort is considered best optimized algorithm which gives $\Theta(n \log n)$ comparisons with $\Theta(n)$ space complexity. Heap Sort is also considered optimized one with hidden structural complexity with $\Omega(n \log n)$ comparisons and $\Theta(n)$ space complexity.

VII. SHORTCOMINGS OF CLASSICAL LOWER BOUND THEOREM FOR SORTING ALGORITHMS

Though Classical Lower Bound Theorem has given quite a fair intuition of the lower limits of time complexities in form of number of comparisons but still it ignores to include following tradeoffs which may infiltrate other areas of requirements:

- Space Complexity: though lower bound theorem addresses time complexity so an exchange of space complexity can be used which may breach the overall requirements? In case of problems of large data sets which take place in bioinformatics, machine learning space complexity is crucial one[11][12][13].
- Processor Complexity: due to the advancement in parallel computing, distributed computing and availability of cloud we should include this aspect also.
- Structural Complexity: there are algorithms which claim to achieve lower bounds but internal movements, adjusting the structure after every single operations may make the a algorithm a victim of structural complexity.
- Stability: some of the algorithms claim to achieve lower bounds eventually. Quick Sort is best example of this. In quick sort for the same problem if we run the algorithm twice or thrice, it may not give the same performance in every try. So such type of stability factor should also be included in lower bound theorem. Rather proposed lower bound theorem advocates that only worst case of stable algorithms should only be considered.

VIII. MODIFIED LOWER BOUND THEOREM FOR SORTING ALGORITHMS

Considering the shortcomings of classical lower bound theorem for comparison based algorithms for sorting here proposed a modified or the more generalized version as:

“Any Stable Sequential Comparison Based sorting algorithm will take at least $\Omega(n \log n)$ comparison in worst case and at least $\Omega(1)$ space”.

The proposed theorem modifies classical theorem in the following manner:

- Addition of the word *Stable* in the beginning we make it clear that there should exist a stable algorithm only not the eventual performer. As the eventual performance are eventual not the consistent one and requirements most of the time expect consistence performance.
- Addition of the word ‘*Sequential*’ before comparison so that it is clear that we are talking about elementary and generic process with the help of single processing element only. If we can achieve sorting efficiently using single processor then we can achieve better cost effective solution using advanced computational resources.
- It adds *Space Complexity* also which further clarifies and establishes the correspondence or tradeoff between time complexity and space complexity.

IX. CONCLUSION

The modified Lower Bound Theorem not only establishes lower bound on comparisons but also establishes lower bound on the use of processors, space and stability. Thus one can have a clear idea on various tradeoffs offered by various algorithms and choose the best one as per requirements.

X. FUTURE SCOPE

To work on an algorithm which can achieve all of the above stated objectives of the lower bound theorem for comparison based sorting or even better than that. We can further modify Heap Sort or Merge Sort or any other algorithm which can best represent or implement modified lower bound theorem.

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